

Effect of time of herbicide application (DS)^a and rice duration in a lowland rice nursery, Coimbatore, India.

Variety	Butachlor 1 kg/ha		Thiobencarb 1 kg/ha		Oxadiazon 0.5 kg/ha		Pendimethalin 1 kg/ha		Control
	5 DS	8 DS	5 DS	8 DS	5 DS	8 DS	5 DS	8 DS	
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (no./0.04 m ²) at 20 DS									
IR50	0.16	0.50	0	0.50	0	0.50	0.16	1.16	3.50
Ponmani	0	0	0.33	0	0	0	0.16	0.50	4.82
Co 43	0	0.60	0	0.16	0	0.16	0.33	1.16	4.33
Mean	0.05	0.36	0.11	0.22	0	0.22	0.22	0.94	4.22
<i>Cyperus difformis</i> (no./0.04 m ²) at 20 DS									
IR50	0.50	0.58	0	0.58	0	0.92	0.75	1.25	4.08
Ponmani	0	0	0.16	0	0	0.16	0.75	0.93	5.08
Co 43	0	1.13	0	0.25	0	0.08	0.83	1.25	4.16
Mean	0.17	0.57	0.05	0.28	0	0.39	0.76	1.14	4.44
<i>Rice height</i> (cm)									
IR50	15.7	17.7	16.3	19.2	14.2	17.0	15.7	17.4	19.9
Ponmani	16.3	20.0	17.1	18.4	17.8	19.6	17.0	18.9	19.4
Co 43	16.1	18.0	17.0	20.0	15.4	18.5	17.2	18.5	20.0
Mean	16.0	18.6	16.8	19.2	15.8	18.9	16.6	18.3	19.8
<i>Rice population</i>									
IR50	65.5	106.5	92.5	132.5	75.0	106.5	111.5	122.0	136.0
Ponmani	78.0	121.0	118.5	136.0	97.5	149.0	83.0	111.5	155.5
Co 43	87.5	122.5	100.0	139.5	77.0	138.0	85.5	120.0	135.0
Mean	77.0	116.6	103.7	136.0	83.2	131.2	93.3	117.8	142.2

^aDS = days after sowing.

	Treatment		Varieties		Interaction	
	SE	CD	SE	CD	SE	CD
1.	0.020	0.056	0.011	0.032	0.034	0.096
2.	0.058	0.163	0.033	0.094	0.100	0.283
3.	0.570	1.621	0.330	0.901	0.984	2.841
4.	0.820	2.330	0.474	1.340	1.421	4.030

germinated seeds were sown 1 d after leveling. Emulsifiable concentrate formulations were mixed with sand (2 kg/1,000 m²) and applied uniformly in 2.5-cm-deep water.

Mean weed data from the nursery (see table) indicated population of annual weeds in the herbicide-treated plots was from 0 to 0.94/0.04 m² for *Echinochloa crus-galli* and from 0 to 1.14/0.04 m² for *Cyperus difformis*. Counts were 4.22 to 4.44/0.04 m² in control plots. The herbicides effectively controlled weed growth. Eighth-d application was more selective than fifth-d application. Selectivity was low with fifth-d application of butachlor or oxadiazon to IR50. □

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Pest control and management OTHER PESTS

Influence of rate and time of carbofuran application to control root-knot nematodes in upland rice

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Root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne incognita* (Kofoid and White) Chitwood causes poor seedling establishment and low rice yields. The effect is more severe under upland conditions. We tested carbofuran for nematode control in a greenhouse experiment.

OS6 seeds were planted in 4 litres of steam-sterilized loamy soil and inoculated

with 1000 root-knot nematode eggs recovered from galled roots of *Celosia* sp. Carbofuran was applied at three rates at

different times (see table) in three replications. Fifty days after planting (DAP), galls and soil nematode population were

Effect of carbofuran on root-knot nematodes in rice, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Treatment	13 DAP		35 DAP	
	Galling index ^a	Nematode population	Galling index ^a	Nematode population
No nematicide	2.7	1738	2.7	1738
Carbofuran 10G 1 kg ai/ha	1.3	837**	1.7	888**
Carbofuran 10G 2 kg ai/ha	1.3	213**	1.3	1475*
Carbofuran 10G 3 kg ai/ha	1.0	238**	1.7	250**
LSD	1% = 93.78		5% = 67.57	

^a0 = no galling system

1 = less than ¼ of root system with small galls

2 = less than ½ of root system with small galls

3 = less than ½ of root system with medium galls

4 = more than ½ of root system with medium galls

counted. Nematode population was determined by thoroughly mixing the soil in each bucket, then taking a 250-cc soil sample for extraction using Baermann's

funnel method.

All rates of carbofuran significantly reduced nematode population. Early application of 2 kg ai/ha performed best.

For late application, 3 kg ai/ha is suggested. There was no phytotoxicity at that rate. □

Entomostracan crustaceans inhabiting rice fields

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We collected 100 samples of aquatic fauna from the rice fields in and around Ludhiana in 1982 summer, and identified species of Entomostraca. There were 2 conchostracans, 4 cladocerans, 15 ostracods, and 6 copepods (see table). □

Entomostraca from rice fields at Ludhiana, India.

Species	Order/Family
<i>Cyclestheria hislopi</i> (Barid)	Order Conchstraca Family Cyclestheriidae
<i>Caenesthereilla indica</i> (Gurney)	Family Cyzicidae
<i>Diaphanosoma sarsi</i> Richard	Order Cladocera Family Sididae
<i>Leydigia acanthocercoides</i> (Fischer)	Family Chydoridae
<i>Moina brachiata</i> (Jurine)	Family Monidae
<i>Macrothrix hirsuticornis</i> Norman and Brady	Family Macrothricidae
<i>Centrocypris bhagirathiae</i> Battish	Class Ostracoda
<i>C. madani</i> Battish	Family Cyprididae
<i>Cypris pubera</i> Muller	
<i>Cypris subglobosa</i> Sowerby	
<i>Cyprinotus cingalensis</i> Brady	
<i>Hemicypris derweshensis</i> Battish	
<i>Hemicypris malerkotlaensis</i> Battish	
<i>Hemicypris pyxidata</i> (Moniez)	
<i>Strandesia elongata</i> Hartmann	
<i>Chrissia</i> sp.	
<i>Stenocypris major</i> (Baird)	
<i>Ilyocypris biphlicata</i> (Koch)	
<i>I. bradyi</i> Sars	
<i>I. dentifera</i> Sars	
<i>I. gibba</i> (Ramdohr)	
<i>Eucyclops speratus</i> (Lilljeborg)	Class Copepoda Order Cyclopoida
<i>Mesocyclops leuckarti</i> (Claus)	
<i>M. tenuis</i> (Marsh)	
<i>Microcyclops dentatimanus</i> (Marsh)	
<i>M. varicans</i> (Sars)	
<i>Phyllodiptomus blanci</i> (Guerne and Richard)	Order Calanoida

Soil and crop management

Residual effects of straw, lime, and manganese dioxide amendments on the chemical kinetics of a flooded iron-toxic soil

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Fertilizer shortages and high fertilizer prices have encouraged research to determine the residual effect of various amendments applied to improve problem soils. To estimate the beneficial and economic effects of CaCO₃, MnO₂, and straw amendments, we need to know how long the residual effects will persist.

We conducted a greenhouse experiment to determine the residual effects of straw (2.5 g/kg soil), CaCO₃ (2.5 g/kg soil), MnO₂ (0.05 g/kg soil) amendments. Soil was collected from the top 20 cm of a Sulfaquept from Malinao, Albay, Philippines. It had pH 3.4, 0.64% organic C, 0.04% total N, 2.4% active Fe, and 0.003% active Mn²⁺. Four 3-wk-old seedlings were transplanted in each Pot in 4 replications, and the soil solution was analyzed every 2 wk.

Straw and CaCO₃ treatment depressed Eh, EC, Fe²⁺, Mn²⁺, and SO₄²⁻

Kinetics of soil solution Fe⁺⁺ as affected by the different residual treatments, IRRI.